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Abstract. International trade is an important part of the global economy, which includes the exchange of services and technologies. The article describes the essence of international trade, the stages of development and its importance in addition to the definition of changes and fixed role in the field of international trade. Development in the field of services and technologies in Uzbekistan will help to study the country's location in international trade.

Keywords: International Trade, Development, Investment, Technology, Infrastructure, Cooperation, integration.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ ТОРГОВЛЯ УСЛУГАМИ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯМИ

Абстрактный. Международная торговля является важной частью мировой экономики, которая включает в себя обмен услугами и технологиями. В статье описывается сущность международной торговли, этапы развития и ее значение, а также определяются изменения и закреплённая роль в сфере международной торговли. Развитие в сфере услуг и технологий в Узбекистане поможет изучить место страны в международной торговле.

Ключевые слова: международная торговля, развитие, инвестиции, технологии, инфраструктура, сотрудничество, интеграция.

International trade is an important branch of the global economy. It represents trade relations and economic integration between countries through the exchange of services and technologies. Developments in the field of international trade have been turning a great roller in expanding the economies of countries. Uzbekistan is also part of the table of countries developing its participation in international trade. In order to strengthen its economic development, the country is determining its place and destination in international trade. International trade ensures the development of Uzbekistan in the field of services and technologies and is important in strengthening its participation in the global market. This article is intended to describe the role and

development of international trade and Uzbekistan in this area, to analyze the important goals and processes in it.

International trade is an important branch of the global economy and exerts its associated essence. This essence can manifest itself in many and different areas. International trade is associated with the basic training of the exchange of goods, services, capital, and technologies between countries. International trade, having different methodologies in its composition and characteristics, is applied to management, economics, sociology and other fields. This type of trade plays a major role in the economic development of countries by strengthening economic ties between countries and increasing financial integration. International trade ensures the exchange of goods and services in international markets. It is a type of trade, a fundamental part of foreign financial activity and helps to expand the economy of foreign countries. International trade processes are usually carried out through Export-import relations and have its own methods and rules. In addition international trade, has a large diversification, which expands trade relations between countries and includes foreign financial activities. The main reasons for this development depend on many factors, such as mutual use, changes in the compatibility of financial systems and the capital environment. It is also an important manifestation of technological innovation. This type of trade constitutes a huge contribution to technological growth and development. Through international trade, countries learn and introduce new technologies to attract investment to emerging sectors. The essence of international trade, with its complexity and role in various fields, is of great importance in the global economy. It is a type of trade that promotes cooperation and interaction between countries and increases market opportunities in the world. International trade, with its dynamics and unchanging characteristics, retains its place in the changed form of the global economy and plays a big role in the economic development of countries.

The stages of development of international trade are one of the sectors in which the global economy has shown itself. These stages are the approximate quarters needed to study, determine, and analyze the level of trade relations and economic integration between countries.

The following stages are important in the development of international trade:

The initial stage, at this stage, is when trade relations between countries are carried out at the simplest level. Imports and exports include the exchange of basic goods and services between small-scale and developing countries.

Expanded Stage, at this stage, the objects and sub-objects of international trade will expand. The spectrum of the exchange of goods and services between countries expands and includes the scale and forms of mutual financial relations. At this stage, global markets and regional economic alliances will become important.

Integration phase, international trade will be strengthened and developed at this stage. The integration phase enhances trade and financial relations between states, the legal and legal framework is improved, implemented through mutual credit systems and currencies.

Expanded integration phase, at which stage international trade expands and intensifies. Economic relations between countries are further reached, new markets are opened and new sectors are developed. International trade at this stage, with its maximum impact and role, raises the level of integration in the global economy.

Each stage is important in the development of international trade and represents the integration processes of the global economy. It is considered as one of the strategic plans for stages, countries and economic organizations and provides ample opportunities for the analysis and targeted management of financial processes around the world.

Trade in services (% of GDP) in World was reported at 13.39 % in 2022, according to the World Bank collection of development indicators, compiled from officially recognized sources. World - Trade in services (% of GDP) - actual values, historical data, forecasts and projections were sourced from the World Bank on June of 2024.

World Trade in services (% of GDP) - %

Source: tradingeconomics.com | World Bank

Uzbekistan is successfully trying to a large extent and further increase in the pursuit of development in the field of services and technologies. International trade and its role in the country's economy, which is of great importance in the development process. To increase the development of Uzbekistan in the field of services and technologies, the following processes are widely analyzed. The government of Uzbekistan pays great attention to attracting investments, implementing legal and financial reforms, and promoting development in the field of services and technologies with the provision of financial forces in the private sphere. The strengthening of infrastructure, especially the development and expansion of the internet and telecommunication networks, is of great importance in strengthening the country's international trade. The economy of Uzbekistan will expand with the role of the digital economy and the application of technological innovations. The strategies, programs and projects used to develop the digital economy are studied and implemented. This process is leading to the growth of the country along with its international trade and its role in the field of services and technologies. Uzbekistan carries out activities aimed at expanding international trade and facilitating access to international markets in order to increase its role and address in international trade. These measures will help strengthen the country's international trade and ensure changes in the country's economy. Related to

development in industry, services and technology, investment, innovation, and support for businesses and startups. The government of Uzbekistan continues to reform laws and regulations to further simplify the business environment. Changes in international trade will strengthen the country's global economic integration. Uzbekistan is engaged in entering new markets, attracting foreign investment and developing international cooperation in order to further strengthen its location in international trade.

To describe the changes and strict position in the field of international trade, changes in various sectors of the global economy and the specific role of Uzbekistan in them should be indicated. Systemic changes in the field of international trade, such as the strengthening of the digital economy, the growth of electronic trading platforms and the implementation of the internet, are examples of changes. This makes it easier to automate sales processes, learn and collect data. Changes in international trade expand trade relations between countries. This will facilitate expansions, opening new markets, integration in global networks, and access to international markets for local companies. The strengthening of legal and financial procedures leads to changes in the field of international trade, strengthening of legal and financial procedures. It is important to regulate trade relations between countries and strengthen financial ties, attract investments and simplify business. Technological innovation, in particular, changes in the field of digital economy and creation, has a huge role in the field of international trade. This leads to innovation, the creation of new services and products and increases the competitiveness of companies in the international market. Changes in international trade will increase cooperation between countries. This will further increase economic integration, facilitate foreign investment, and strengthen participation among countries in the global economy. These definitions have been extensively covered to provide a general understanding of changes in international trade and their strict role. Changes in the field of international trade, along with dynamics in the global economy and processes in different sectors, will change and create great opportunities for countries.

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